

BIM INTEGRATION IN ARCHITECTURAL EDUCATION: BRIDGING THE INDUSTRY-ACADEMIA GAP IN KHYBER PAKHTUNKHWA, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Introduction: BIM is progressively replacing the traditional methodology in the architecture, engineering, and construction industries internationally.

Significance: Its significance is more evident in the reduction of frequently occurring errors in designing, understanding of buildings, visualization, clash detection in construction processes, and better communication among various cross-disciplinary collaborations.

Objectives: The primary objective of this research is to evaluate the BIM Competency gap among the graduate architects in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and the identification of the interventions in academic curricula that need to be aligned with the global BIM practices.

Methodology: The methodology adopted for this research is an empirical analysis surveying how the curriculum at the undergraduate level could integrate the BIM.

Results: There is usage of 2D and 3D computer-aided design subjects in the curriculum and elective subjects offered to enhance their integration. But there is a pressing need for a structured framework to incorporate and integrate Building Information Modelling (BIM) into undergraduate curricula in Pakistan. This requires various stakeholders - governmental policy makers, academicians, and design consultants- to collaborate in aligning the quality of architectural education at par with international trends and demands.

Implication: The BIM adoption will enhance success rates in national and international AEC industry initiatives.

INTRODUCTION

Building information modelling (BIM) is a technique and technology that uses digital objects and coordinated data on their behaviour to analyse building models. Notwithstanding its difficulties, BIM is well known for its many advantages in the Architecture, Engineering, and Construction (AEC) sector. The benefit of using BIM encompasses the various venues, such as increasing quality management and enhancing performance, detecting

clashes at earlier stages, and diminishing the chances of conflict at a later stage of the project. Teamwork and better communication, along with the sequential documentation and presentation of the data, design, and its visualization. All these benefits are responsible for the saving of capital and time, which is crucial for any project.

Traditionally use of computer-aided design and drawings has paved the way for the use of building

information modelling BIM. BIM is used to digitally represent the physical qualities with the functional phenomenon by incorporating smart objects having rich data attributes. It provides a better way to understand planning, designing, and operation throughout the life cycle of a Building. It can be represented in various forms, starting from 3D digital visualizations to 7D Sustainability. Right before construction commencement, the BIM can assist all the stakeholders, including architects, engineers, contractors, and operation and maintenance personnel, with the various potential conflicts, clashes, and their solutions well in time. Moreover, these issues are represented in a visual format, which is very easy for stakeholders to understand quickly and communicate with the concerned quarters for earlier solutions to the issues. The visualization feature of the BIM is also very helpful for the students to identify, study, and solve the various problems that can arise in geometry, and the design stage/

As the architecture, engineering, construction, and Operation & Maintenance industry is adopting BIM in their complex projects throughout the world, academia linked with these fields is also busy in embedding the BIM courses in their curriculum, frameworks, and specializations.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

1. CONCEPT OF BIM:

Technology is advancing rapidly, as we are moving fast through the 4th revolution of industry. This revolution is also adopted throughout the architecture, engineering and construction, and maintenance industries. BIM is the key factor in transforming the AECO by incorporating enhanced methods for designing, documenting, and executing building construction. BIM started in 1957 with Computer Aided Machining (CAM) and evolved into Computer Aided Design/Drafting (CAD) in the early 60s (Goubau, 2012).

Traditional CAD had limitations, as it mainly represented lines and arcs like a drawing board, offering limited benefits to consultants, contractors, and clients (Karen & Douglas, 2014). Unlike CAD, BIM focuses on the building process rather than just drafting (Ibrahim, 2006). By the 1980s, 3D CAD brought significant changes to the AEC industry, and

BIM introduced a new way of thinking about building design (Quirk, 2017).

BIM's main objective is to provide a platform in the form of the creation of an intelligent Database that can equally be available for the stakeholders involved to get a unified approach for a project. (Smith & Tardif, 2009). It integrates all disciplines and systems of a building into a single virtual model, enhancing collaboration and efficiency (Azhar, 2011). BIM's power lies in its central source of information, which supports collaboration for a common goal.

In the early 2000s, Building Information Modelling (BIM) emerged in the Architecture, Engineering, and Construction (AEC) industry to address low productivity and innovation barriers (Egan, 1998; Teicholz, 2004). BIM introduced a collaborative model that represented the physical characteristics of buildings throughout different project phases. It is a complex, multi-dimensional information model where building elements retain their symbolic and abstract meanings through both qualitative and quantitative data. These data types are linked to the information model and are known as BIM dimensions, such as 3D modelling, 4D time, 5D cost, 6D performance, and other (n)D facilities.

Today, Building Information Modelling (BIM) is becoming essential in the Architecture, Engineering, and Construction (AEC) industry. Consulting companies, contractors, clients, and facilities managers are recognizing the benefits of using a central database for their buildings (Azhar, 2011; Eastman, 2011). The demand for BIM has increased, with governments and multinational companies leading its implementation (Howard & Björk, 2008).

2. BIM & Sustainability:

BIM is an effective tool that aids building owners and operators throughout a structure's life cycle by promoting sustainability, offering visual context to performance data, enabling environmental impact assessment, and accessing projects focused on energy efficiency. Sustainability can be adopted in architectural education following various routes (Ali et al., 2022). The AEC industry has traditionally been slow to adopt technology, but is now increasingly integrating BIM. Both CAD and BIM are forms of computer-aided building modelling, with BIM offering up to six-dimensional models (Bryde et al.,

2013). BIM supports the entire life cycle of a facility, enhancing long-term gains for organizations that invest in it.

BIM has been progressively adopted by the design and facility management industries due to its wide spectrum of benefits. Also, the approaches towards quality of life are driven by the various factors such as environments, safety, health, along infrastructure. The energy costs and sustainability issues are compelling the building owner towards the adoption of BIM for better performance and management (Takim et al., 2013).

3. BIM & Collaboration:

Building Information Modelling (BIM) integrates different disciplines within a common environment that is essential for collaboration, which in turn leads to project success (Succar, 2009). As we know the most of the challenging tasks while working on a project is the better communication, coordination and cooperation of the various stakeholders to get the prompt action and get the desired results, BIM is equipped with such a critical facility to identify the clashes, communicate it visually to all the stakeholders concerned and the proper solution is suggested with the help of the each player involved. This is the main idea for better and timely decision-making and getting what is desired, and maintaining the chance of better returns on the investment. Collaboration is achieved when all parties' self-interests align with project objectives, emphasizing the need for both knowledge and technology.

4. BIM and Visualization:

Using the BIM, one can visualize the project from scratch to the renderings. It encompasses the conceptual design development and the refinement of the product to the last stages of the building design. This is the most decisive feature of BIM that is responsible for the contemporary architecture design (Corke, 2021). It can transform the limitation of the hidden lines to ambiance in interior and exterior and enabling the designers and users to visualize the spaces more efficiently. This adds value to the design and communication to avoid any misunderstanding at a later stage of the design process.

Traditionally, architects have to rely on manual visualization media such as sketches, perspectives, and

still images for conveying their ideas to various stakeholders. Later, it was enhanced by incorporating the 3D Visualization, but with the introduction of the BIM enhanced visualization, the architects can provide detailed insights to the various stages of design to the clients, and other stakeholders to make timely decisions, and ensure the success of projects. It is a handy tool to convey the design ideas effectively in a complex project with fostering collaboration and coordination throughout the life of the project.

5. BIM and Management:

The integration of BIM within a construction project is instrumental in enhancing the various processes for the betterment of the overall project. If we take the management point of view, BIM has proven its worth by increasing the value of the projects. It has reduced the duration of the project construction by streamlining the process, detecting the clashes between various critical processes, and enabling the decision-making process to be timely and efficient.

Moreover, BIM is used to determine the accurate quantities of the materials and used to project the accurate estimates for the project costs, which are essential for efficient budgeting and allocation of resources to each project task. It is useful to minimize the waste, control the cost, and keep the project financially on track. BIM is also used to optimize the overall performance of the building, by being maintained and operated throughout its life cycle (Eastman, 2011).

Adoption of the BIM in Design, Construction, and Maintenance of buildings is very crucial, beneficial, and sustainable for all stakeholders.

6. BIM and Life Cycle Assessment:

Life-cycle assessment (LCA) is an in-depth analysis of the environmental impacts of buildings, materials, and assemblies, though it is relatively new and complex for many professionals. Traditionally, LCAs were conducted post-construction rather than during the design phase, where BIM data could influence decisions. While BIM models should theoretically facilitate LCAs, they often lack comprehensive ingredient details. For instance, a BIM model may recognize a steel assembly but not account for the concrete used. LCAs can quantify emissions and

embodied environmental impacts (Nushi & Basha-Jakupi, 2017).

BIM integration in Architectural Education:

Tertiary education, also known as third-stage or post-secondary education, follows secondary education. Within AECO departments, integrating BIM into curricula is crucial to meet industry requirements. TEIs should deliver BIM education at various course levels and expand curricula to include different collaboration modes.

Building Information Modelling (BIM) is a major digital technology in the architecture, engineering, and construction (AEC) industry and a significant theme in AEC higher education. Understanding BIM education trends is crucial for three main reasons: educators must update AEC curricula to give students modern digital skills and broader capabilities; BIM is essential to the global AEC industry's digitalization for improved project efficiency; and the gap between

institutional education and industry needs must be bridged (Tang et al. 2015).

Building Information Modelling (BIM) in Architectural Education in Pakistan:

Throughout the country, the Higher Education Commission and the Pakistan Council of Architects and Town Planners are responsible for the guidelines and curriculum updating of undergraduate and postgraduate curricula of architecture. They have updated their guidelines in 2007, 2013, and 2025. These are all meant to be revised every three years, but these changes are incorporated in almost a decade's time frame.

If we look at various guidelines, in 2007-08, the integration of AutoCAD was made mandatory in the curriculum, the 2D and 3D visualization. While the universities were given the freedom to select any courses as elective subjects and optional subjects, depending on the expertise of the teaching faculty.

Figure 1: Pie chart showing the allocation of HEC/PCATP-mandated courses in the B.Arch curriculum 2007-08.

Every university is bound to offer Computer Applications in the form of Auto CAD, Sketchup, and 3D Studio Max in the range of 04 credit hours in the overall 170 credit hours of the B.Arch Degree.

In 2012-13, the curriculum was revised again to incorporate the latest trends in industry and requirements of the field. If we review the curriculum, the total number of mandatory credit hours was set with a range of 170-180 credits. The core or

compulsory courses credit hours was set to be above 82 credits. Allied sciences and Technologies credit hours were set at 22 credits at minimum, History, Theory, and Critical analysis were set at 20 credits, and the professional practice and communication tools were set at 18 credits at minimum. The Digital Tools for architects were set again at 4 credits minimum with the freedom for schools to enhance their incorporation as Elective subjects.

Figure 2: Pie chart showing the allocation of HEC/PCATP-mandated courses in the B.Arch curriculum 2012-13.

BIM Integration at Khyber Pakhtunkhwa following 2012-13 HEC/PCATP Guidelines:

We have three universities in the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa that are offering architecture education at the Undergraduate level.

The older university that has pioneered in offering the B.Arch degree in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa is the University of Engineering and Technology Peshawar, Abbottabad campus. Following the HEC/PCATP 2012-13 guidelines, they are offering the digital applications in architecture comprising 06 credit hours of compulsory subject stream, while there is also an option for offering it in the elective subject courses as per the needs and requirements of the students (University of Engineering and Technology (UET) Peshawar, n.d.).

In CECOS University, while following B. Arch 2012-13 curriculum guidelines of HEC/PCATP have dedicated 06 credit hours to Digital Tools for architects subjects. 04 credits are allocated in compulsory requirements, while 02 credits are assigned in addition to these 04 credits with the name of Advanced Computer application for architects (Architecture - CECOS University, n.d.).

The much younger institute that is offering the B.Arch degree program is Hazara University, Mansehra. Here, the situation is the same while strictly adhering to the HEC/PCATP 2012-13 Curriculum guidelines, they are offering the courses of 04 credits of compulsory courses while the 03 credits of elective courses with the name of advanced visual graphics (Digital) (Hazara University, n.d.).

Comparison of the integration level at the Policy level and the institutional Level in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa:

While concluding the overall course review, the scheme of studies, and credit hours allocation to the Building Information Modelling (BIM) Education, there is a lack of integration. The overall courses are much higher, and only 4% credits are allocated for the Digital applications. If we further analyze the course contents of these 4% courses, two courses, which are 04 credits, are comprised of Auto CAD, 3D Studio Max, Sketchup, and Adobe Photoshop subjects, while only 02 or 03 credit hours are allocated to the Revit Architecture, i.e., Representing BIM.

While taking the debate further, while interacting with the faculty members from all these institutions, we came to know that there is a dire need to allot much higher credits than only 02 to 03 credits. Some think that contemporary Artificial Intelligence has replaced aging software like Photoshop. Furthermore, they think that Revit needs to be used as a primary design software instead of the classical use of AutoCAD.

The debate was also extended to the graduates who are working in offices. In Pakistan, the architects working in various offices are of the opinion that currently, there is no trend of BIM in smaller, residential, and retail projects. While it is applied in some offices that have larger projects, but at a very basic level. While those graduates who are working in the Gulf Countries and advanced countries like the US and Canada, for instance, are more of the view that BIM is the future of architectural projects. And

they are very much advocates for the BIM integration at Bachelor's level and suggested allocating at least a medium level, not as a beginner-level course introduction.

HEC/PCATP Revised Curriculum Guideline 2025:

The Curriculum was revised in 2025, where the undergraduate policy 2023 was formally adopted in the Architecture and duly worked out nationally with the help of the Council, Academicians, and practicing architects.

General Education was made compulsory to have a minimum of 32 credit hours, Architectural Design Studios needed to have 76 Credit Hours, Building Technology having 20 Credit Hours, Professional

Practice related subjects 18 credits, Allied Subjects 14 credits, Interdisciplinary Subjects 12 credits, and Elective 8 Credits.

If we compare the last three decades and curriculum guidelines set forth and implementation monitored by HEC/ PCATP through Accreditation process on Yearly basis, the compulsory percentage of the credit hours dedicated to the integration of Digital technologies i.e. Computer Aided Design is 02 percent, 02 percent and 04 percent respectively in the guidelines of 2007-08, 2012-13, and 2024-25. Besides these compulsory subjects, the digital tools for architects can be offered in various 2 credit or 3 credit hours of Elective subjects following the individual school's own Board of studies recommendations.

Figure 3: Pie chart showing the allocation of HEC/PCATP-mandated courses in the B.Arch curriculum 2024-25.

Discussion:

The study aims to check the overall curriculum guidelines issued and implemented by the HEC/PCATP as a statutory body for the incorporation of the standards in Architecture education throughout Pakistan, while emphasizing its implementation in the context of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

This study has identified a critical gap in the integration of BIM education in the undergraduate B.Arch Degree program in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP), Pakistan, in comparison to the international Architecture, Engineering, Construction, and

Operation industries. On the global scale, AECO industries uses BIM for the enhancement of collaboration, sustainability, and Life-cycle management. While the academic institutions are merely constrained by the rigidity of the curriculum, allocating about 2 to 4 percent of credits to digital tools-primarily focused on the basic Computer Aided Design CAD rather than BIM, Technology, and methodologies. Empirical analysis suggested that only 1.2 to 1.8 percent of the total credit hours are allocated to BIM Courses (e.g., Revit Architecture), which is drastically short of industrial demands at a global scale.

The key challenges included the curricular deficits comprising over-reliance on obsolete software (AutoCAD, Photoshop, 3ds Max) versus BIM platforms (Revit, Navisworks, Vectorworks works etc) and less emphasis on the BIM dimensions such as scheduling, costing, and sustainability.

The disconnect of the various stakeholders, such as academia, industry, students, and policy makers, from BIM Proficiency. This gap is aggravated by a lack of pedagogy, training, and infrastructure redundancy.

On the policy level, HEC/PCATP revised the curriculum in February 2025 and recommended the interdisciplinary courses. However, this update lacks BIM integration and enforcement mechanisms. Furthermore, HEC/PCATP should adopt international standards from bodies, such as RIBA and NAAB, to periodically update and incorporate revisions into its guidelines.

Serious efforts are also required from institutions offering architecture education throughout Pakistan to address these gaps, understand their causes, and prioritize implementing their solutions.

Conclusions:

In conclusion, we can say that BIM is not just a technology or Tool, but a shift in Paradigm redefining the practice of architecture globally. In Pakistan, especially Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, institutions need reconfiguration of the curricula to enhance the BIM-Literate architects embedded with the skills for sustainable building design and environmental conditions.

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